

Achieving Assistive Human-Robot Cooperation in Industrial Tasks: Design and Control of High-Payload Cooperative Robot

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1. EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Empowering humans is highly demanded in robotic research and practice [1, 2]. An ever-increasing range of applications (*e.g.*, rehabilitation, military) is focusing on such important issue, improving the daily life of people (*e.g.*, improving motor skills, task's ergonomy, human power) [3]. Industries are one of the key user for the development of such technology [4]. Nowadays, many onerous tasks (*e.g.*, lifting/installation of heavy components [5]) are still manually made, implying non-ergonomic postures and musculoskeletal disorders [6, 7]. Indeed, robotics is fastly moving conceiving both standard manipulators and wearable devices to improve the working conditions of humans, while increasing production flexibility and productivity [8, 9].

1.1. Related Works

Since empowering devices require to satisfy both task performance and safety requirements, actuation plays a key role in their design [10]. In particular, considering the required direct physical interaction between human and robot systems, stiff actuation is not suitable for highly versatile and safe task execution. Therefore, the development of compliant actuators has been grown, because of their ability to safely interact with the user while storing/releasing energy in passive elastic elements. Considering industrial empowering robotic systems, the most adopted compliant actuators architectures

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are related to SEAs, PEAs and VSAs solutions, and their combination [11].

20 SEAs [12, 13] use a passive mechanical spring in series with a motor, that acts as a low-pass filter for shock loads and thus reduces high gear forces. While this architecture is not suitable for high bandwidth tasks due to their fixed compliance (their related spring constant is commonly selected to achieve a soft behavior [12]), SEAs are characterized by high shock tolerance, low reflected inertia, accurate and stable force control
25 (turning the issue to position control design) and potential energy storage capabilities. SEAs are commonly proposed in lower-limb exoskeletons, where the spring allows for the energy-efficient and quasi-passive walking behavior [14], but also upper-limb applications can be found [15, 16].

PEAs [17] differ from SEAs actuators by using a passive mechanical spring in parallel
30 with a motor. The intuitive idea of such actuation is that spring-like elements generate

Figure 1: DDA applied to the shoulder joint of a cooperative robot device to empower the capabilities. Concept.

most of the nominal torque required along a desired trajectory, so the control efforts of the original actuators can be mainly spent in stabilizing the motion [18]. Such actuation solutions are therefore commonly adopted to reduce the energy consumption of robotic systems while performing repetitive tasks, as described in [19] where a compliant element in parallel to the motor is used to store energy to be used during the repetitive motion to reduce power consumption. The drawback of such common applications is related to the fixed equilibrium position(s) of the actuation system, requiring the motor to continuously provide energy to maintain another target position(s). Moreover, such solutions are not usually exploited when gravity loads have to be compensated.

In [20] SEA and PEA are compared to investigate the potential reduction in power and torque demands on actuators, highlighting that the combination of SEAs and PEAs can yield advantageous power/energy characteristics to be exploited in robotic systems. In [21] a SEA solution is compared with a PEA solution and with a combined SE+PEA solution (a PEA in series with an elastic element SE, involving only one motor) to analyze peak-power and energy-requirements in a prosthetic device for mimicking human ankle joint in walking and running activities. In [22] a SPEA (in which a motor is capable of variable in-series recruitment of multiple parallel elastic elements) is proposed to reduce the motor torque requirements having the possibility to independently pre-tensioning the multiple parallel elastic elements (*i.e.*, obtaining a higher output torque as the sum of each contribution from the single parallel elastic element), as such the motor can be downscaled and the efficiency can be drastically increased.

Variable stiffness actuators [23, 24] are specifically designed for human-robot interaction tasks. Each actuator consists of two motors and spring arrangement and allows control over displacement as well as joint stiffness. Introducing a possibility to change the stiffness of the joint while the robot is operating permits a further enhancement of the skills of a joint. Similar to a human, who can change the stiffness of his joints by straining the agonist and the antagonist, the stiffness can be changed according to the performed task. Performance of VSA is dependent on range of compliance variation at the joint [25, 26]. However, the continuous variation of joint stiffness causes a major complexity of the VSA mechanism and control, contrary to the quite easy to implement SEA/PEA architecture [27].

1.2. Contribution

Considering industrial empowering applications (*i.e.*, involving heavy components), the aim of this contribution is to describe the design of an actuation solution to be applied at the shoulder joint of an empowering robotic system (*i.e.*, the joint with the higher applied load) in order to bear high torques (both from gravity and dynamic effects) while preserving its reduced size/weight properties both for safety and usability issues.

The proposed mechanism aims at actively assisting the human operator during cooperative tasks while implementing a compliant actuation system, and it consists in a Dual Driven Actuation (DDA) architecture, defining a parallel system composed by (i) a serial elastic actuator (SEA) and by (ii) a standard direct actuator. Such solution defines a redundant actuation system, decoupled by the elastic element of (i), capable to manage the energy flow by control. While (i) is capable to apply high-amplitude low-frequency torques (since the bandwidth is limited by its compliant element), (ii) allows to actively assist the human operator by applying high-frequency torques, improving the transparency of the human-robot interaction (*i.e.*, limiting the human-exercised forces on the robotic system) and achieving a high-precision positioning of the joint. Moreover, on the basis of the proposed architecture, a zero-torque controller can be also designed for (ii), allowing a direct guidance of the joint, exploiting the capabilities of the SEA actuation. The proposed DDA has resulted in a compact and low-installed-power solution, feasible to be applied in a limited-space scenario. The DDA architecture has been applied in simulation to a high-payload (*i.e.*, > 25 kg) cooperative robotic device to empower the capabilities of human in industrial tasks execution (Figure 1). The control of such robotic system has been proposed to compensate for the actuation elasticity while positioning the manipulator lifting a heavy component, resulting in a low-installed-power solution.

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